

**CONSERVATION OF PRIORITY SPECIES OF
MARINE MEGAFUNA
IN GREECE AND ITALY**

Implementation and Monitoring Plan for the pilot
conservation actions

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LIFE22-NAT-EL-LIFE MareNatura

“Conservation of priority species of marine megafauna in Greece and Italy”

Grant Agreement Project 101113792 –

LIFE22-NAT-EL-LIFE MareNatura – LIFE-2022-SAP-NAT

Title:	Implementation and Monitoring Plan for the pilot conservation actions
Delivery date:	6 May 2026
Work package/Task:	WP6 - Monitoring and evaluation of the project / T6.1 Monitoring at key N2K sites the impact of the pilot concrete conservation action on the target species
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Dissemination Level:		
PU	Public — fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

Change Records

Version	Date	Changes
1.0	31 May 2025	First draft

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1.1	31 March 2026	Revisions on the monitoring of the impact sections on Rat eradication & Nest protection
1.2	6 May 2026	Final additions from authors
1.3	17 June 2026	Minor corrections on 2.2.1 and additions in Appendix

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1. Introduction

This document presents a consolidated overview of three pilot conservation actions implemented under the LIFE MareNatura project, as part of Work Package 4 (WP4) – “Sustainability, replication and exploitation of project results” and Task 4.4 “Implementation of a Marine Conservation School demonstrating best practice techniques”. These pilot actions focus on practical, site-based conservation efforts targeting priority marine species and habitats within Natura 2000 sites in Greece. Specifically, the actions include:

- The restoration of monk seal (*Monachus monachus*) breeding caves,
- The protection of loggerhead sea turtle (*Caretta caretta*) nests,
- The eradication of invasive rats (*Rattus* spp.) from key seabird breeding habitats.

Each of these actions is presented in detail in the subsequent sections and is based on technical reports submitted by the implementing partners: MOM, ARCHELON, and the University of Crete in collaboration with NCC. The purpose of this document is to provide a unified technical summary that supports both internal project coordination and external communication, including future evaluation, transferability, and potential replication.

These three pilot conservation actions are both thematically and operationally integrated into Work Package 4 (WP4) of the LIFE MareNatura project, specifically under the task “Implementation of a Marine Conservation School demonstrating best practice techniques”. The pilot conservation actions will be implemented in the framework of the training sessions of the Marine Conservation School (MCS) and aim to the practical training of the members of the MCS by implementing best practice techniques in the field. On the other hand, the conservation actions are expected to directly impact the conservation status of the three target species: the Mediterranean monk seal, the loggerhead turtle and the Scopoli’s shearwater. The present Implementation and Monitoring Plan of the pilot actions — restoration of monk seal breeding caves, protection of sea turtle nests, and eradication of invasive rats — serves as documentation of the applied conservation actions, including the objectives, expected results and methods for both implementation and monitoring of the actions.

The three pilot conservation actions presented in this document demonstrate targeted and site-specific interventions aiming to improve the conservation status of priority marine species within Greece’s Natura 2000 network. Implemented under the LIFE Mare Natura project, these actions provide tangible examples of applied conservation practice in the field.

By combining technical feasibility, ecological relevance, and collaborative implementation,

each pilot offers valuable insights into the development of effective management strategies for marine biodiversity. The experience gained through these pilot interventions is expected to contribute to broader conservation efforts, both within Greece and across the Mediterranean region.

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2. Implementation and Monitoring Plan

2.1 Monk Seal Breeding Cave Restoration

Threatened with imminent extinction, the Mediterranean monk seal (*Monachus monachus*) faces several serious threats. Understanding the nature and magnitude of these threats and finding effective ways to mitigate them is of utmost importance for the conservation of the species. Currently Mediterranean monk seals use for giving birth, exclusively marine caves with specific morphological characteristics. The main feature of the caves that seals use to give birth to their young is the existence of an inner beach (made of sand or pebbles). Data from IR cameras have shown that breeding females compete for the limited space (internal beach area in the pupping caves) available (MOM unpublished data). Maintaining these beaches in good condition is therefore of utmost importance for the conservation of the species. The degradation of the quality of this important habitat can occur in many ways, the most common of which are: a) covering part or all the beach area with marine litter b) the disappearance of part or the entire beach due to wave action. Both phenomena result in a reduction in the surface area available for seals to give birth and nurture their young. The result is a reduction in seal activity (fewer births) and, in the worst case, the complete abandonment of the cave. Restoration of breeding caves is therefore considered as the enlargement of the surface of the inner beach that can be used by the animals either by removing the litter or by enlarging the beach by technical means. Both restoration actions are considered concrete conservation actions for the species as they can have the effect of increasing the degree of use by seals and ultimately increasing the number of seal births in an area.

In the context of the LIFE MareNatura project, restorations will be carried out through the removal of marine litter from the interior of sea caves. The restorations will be carried out in cooperation with NECCA and will have, apart from their immediate effect, they will act as capacity building for NECCA staff to carry them out in the future where necessary. It should be noted that a baseline study conducted by MOM before this project, showed clearly that the litter load in caves used by the seals for pupping can be significant, thus degrading considerably the quality of the habitat.

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Figure 1. A weaned monk seal pup among an impressive number of marine debris that has accumulated in a breeding cave. © P. Dendrinis/MOM

The debris is mainly concentrated on the surface of the internal beaches of the caves, where it is usually deposited due to the waves' action. In addition, debris is floating or lying on the sea floor inside the caves as well as outside of cave entrances.

In the context of this action, the removal and management of marine plastic debris and derelict fishing gear from at least 3 important pupping sites will be implemented in the framework of the "Implementation of a Marine Conservation School" and the "Marine Conservation Task Force".

2.1.1. Objectives of the action

- Direct objectives: gradual reduction of the amount of marine litter deposited and accumulated in the caves and enlargement of the dry surface of the available pupping habitat
- Indirect objectives: (a) Increase in the use of the marine cave for resting/pupping, (b) Increase in the number of births.

2.1.2. Target species

Monachus monachus is the species that will benefit from this action.

2.1.3. Areas of implementation

The action will take place in two NATURA 2000 sites GR3000017 (PARAKTIA KAI THALASSIA

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ZONI MAKRONISOU) and GR1430004 (ETHNIKO THALASSIO PARKO ALONNISOU – VOREION SPORADON, ANATOLIKI SKOPELOS). Additionally, cave restoration actions will be implemented in a cave in Karpathos island which is not located within a NATURA2000 network area but which is located in an important monk seal area around Karpathos island and Astakonisia islets, a known pupping hub which can benefit from additional connectivity between the currently available habitats.

Figure 2. Areas of implementation

2.1.4. Time period of implementation

Restoration work, which includes the removal of solid debris, will be carried out before the seal breeding season to avoid disturbing the animals.

2.1.5 Methods and protocols

During the approach to the caves and prior to the start of work, the cave will be traced for the presence of animals. The method of collecting and removing marine litter from sea caves involves the systematic visual scanning of the terrestrial part of the caves, which are important resting and breeding grounds for Mediterranean seals.

Litter removal will be done mainly by hand. In cases where the waste will be of such a size as

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to make manual removal impossible, special equipment will be used to cut and remove it (a rechargeable wheel with a cutting disc). In addition, litter will be removed from the surface of the cave's sea wall and around the entrance. The litter found will be collected in rubbish bags. After the cleaning process is completed, the waste will be sorted by type, separated into recyclable and non-recyclable waste, and disposed of appropriately.

The transport of personnel, equipment, waste collection materials and waste collected to and from the islands will be carried out by speedboat. Entry into the caves shall be by swimming, small inflatable boats or kayaks. Cleaning will be carried out by MOM's personnel suitably trained for field work in caves and by Conservation School's participants in cases where these two actions can be combined.

Figure 3. Removing marine litter from a beach of a monk seal pupping site. © P. Dendrinou/MOM

2.1.6. Expected results

The implementation of this action is expected to:

- Decrease of the marine litter covering the internal beaches of the monk seal shelters,
- Increase of the available beach surface for use by the seals,
- Increase of the use of the habitat (subset of habitat type 8330 suitable for the species) by the seals (for resting / pupping).

2.1.7. Monitoring of the impact of the action

The monitoring of the impact of this action will be achieved through the systematic monitoring of the restored caves, using infrared (IR) cameras and/or direct visits to measure changes in the frequency of use by seals. Preparatory work for this project has indicated that

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the targeted caves are currently not used or used very rarely because of the accumulated debris. Any increase in seal presence will be a great success for this action. We don't necessarily expect pupping to occur immediately, or within the timeframe of the project (which would be the highest form of success), but an increase in use will familiarize seals with these caves and hopefully lead to pup rearing in them in the future (monitored long-term after the end of the project as part of MOM's regular population monitoring).

IR cameras that are deployed in the rough environment of marine caves need to be protected by waterproof casings in order to ensure the proper functioning of the system and prevent marine spray and salt from progressively covering the camera lens and hindering its operation. The cameras are installed during periods of low in-cave seal activity and are then collected (or have their SD cards replaced) after the main monk seal pupping season. The cameras remain active for around 5-6 months through at least 2 breeding seasons, recording data either at regular intervals of 1-1.5h (time lapse) or by using a motion-activated photograph and video capture method. The choice between the two depends on the cave layout affecting the camera's coverage and exposure to rough conditions, as well as a prediction of expected activity (which can affect battery life when using motion-activated photography). The photographs are analyzed visually by a human researcher after every SD card collection round for the presence of animals, the identification of individuals, and, most importantly, for the presence of pupping activity taking place in these caves.

During the follow-up cave visitations as part of the monitoring scheme (to change the SD cards on the cameras, or maintain/change cameras as required), through inspections for evidence of seal use are performed. MOM's researchers search for the presence of recent signs of cave use, such as tracks, scats, pieces of fur, or blood. If a seal is encountered in the cave, photographs or video are taken to enable future individual identification. Adults are identified based on the natural pelage scarring and their stage of development. Pups are identified based on their stage of development, as well as the presence of the sexually dimorphic patch of fur on their ventral side. To minimize disturbance to the species, the caves are inspected and their morphological features recorded during times when in-cave seal activity in Greece is lowest.

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Final report of the removal of marine litter from the marine and coastal environment of Andros Island which was implemented in the framework of the action C4 "Habitat improvement measures for the Mediterranean Monk Seal, Mediterranean Shag and Audouin's Gull" of the LIFE Project "Conservation of priority species and habitats of Andros Island protected area integrating socioeconomic considerations" (LIFE 16 NAT/GR/000606).

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2.2 Nest Protection for Loggerhead Sea Turtle

2.2.1. Objectives of the action

- Direct objectives: Protect loggerhead nests laid within the core nesting area of Kyparissia Bay against predation by mammals (e.g. foxes, feral dogs, etc.)
- Indirect objectives: (a) ensure that as many hatchlings as possible are recruited to the population, (b) protection of nests against human use of the habitat for recreational purposes.

2.2.2. Target species

- *Caretta caretta* is the species that will benefit from this action.
- *Vulpes vulpes* (main species responsible for predated nests)
- *Canis lupus familiaris*, *Canis aureus*, *Sus scrofa* (species secondarily responsible for predated nests in the area)

2.2.3. Areas of implementation

Kyparissia Bay (37.3399°N, 21.6952°E) on the west coast of the Peloponnese, Greece, features a 44 km nesting beach. The southernmost 9.5 km of this beach concentrates about 84% of Loggerhead nesting and has been characterized as the core nesting area of Kyparissia Bay (Figure 4). An average of about 2,140 clutches have been deposited annually at the core area (2009 – 2023) with an increasing trend.

The significant increase in the number of clutches annually laid on the site has implications impacting the implementation of the pilot conservation action as presented in the proposal. Specifically, the extremely high nest density along O (Kalo Nero) and A (Vounaki) sectors does not allow for the fencing of nests to occur at full scale due to the high risk of damaging surrounding clutches. As a result, the pilot activity will focus on B (Agiannakis) and C (Elaia), targeting 50% or more of the total number of clutches deposited along these sectors. Total length of the action is estimated at 9.05km, as follows: B Sector - 2.200m, C Sector - 2.600m, D Sector - 4.250m.

To compensate for the exclusion of a significant portion of the core area, the action will be expanded to the beach directly north of the border with Elaia sector). With approximately 750 clutches (mean 2019-23) annually deposited along sector D we are confident that optimal results will be achieved through the implementation of nest protection activities.

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Figure 4. Sketch map of the nesting of Kyparissia Bay, Greece. The core nesting area includes sectors O through C (Kalo Nero through Elaia) (Map from Margaritoulis and Rees 2001)

2.2.4. Time period of implementation

The sea turtle reproductive season usually starts in mid-May with the start of egg-laying and continues through October when the last hatchlings emerge from the nests and reach the sea. Fencing of the nests to protect them from predation needs to occur during the egg-laying season (mid-May – mid-August).

2.2.5 Methods and protocols

The methods applied to protect clutches from predation by mammals will follow guidelines and recommendations made in the Marine Turtle Specialist Group' Research and Management Techniques Manual (Eckert et al. 1999) adapting protocols used during the LIFE Nature project "Application of Management Plan for *Caretta caretta* in southern Kyparissia Bay" (LIFE98NAT/GR/005262). These protocols have significantly contributed to the recovery of the population on the site as reflected in the increasing number of nests (Appendix).

As described in these protocols, once the exact location of the egg chamber has been identified, a metal grid will be placed centrally over the clutch. The grid will be approx. 1m x 1m to ensure maximum protection and to avoid piercing of the eggs by the stakes that will be used to anchor the grid thus preventing access to the eggs when mammals attempt to predate the nest. Each grid is secured through metal or bamboo stakes preventing mammals from accessing the clutch by digging along the sides (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Application of grid to prevent predation of nests by mammals

Once the grid and placement of stakes are complete, the nest code is indicated in several places including a stone placed directly behind the nest and furnished with a sign informing the public that it is a loggerhead turtle nest. These signs are attached to vertical poles or tripods associated with the nest. The nest will continue to be monitored throughout the incubation of the eggs and will be excavated to assess its success and estimate the number of hatchlings that emerged safely reaching the sea.

2.2.6. Expected results

The implementation of fencing of nests to prevent predation by mammals in Kyparissia Bay is already showing success since a steady increase in the number of clutches laid annually has been on the increase during the last 15+ years since the completion of the last LIFE Nature project (LIFE98NAT/GR/005262). The implementation of this action is expected to:

- Reduce the total number of predated nests from the total recorded in the area
- Increase the number of hatchlings that reach the water following the safe incubation of the eggs
- Reduced nest damage inflicted as a result of human use of the site for recreational

purposes

The above is expected to ensure the viability of the population in the future.

2.2.7. Monitoring of the impact of the action

The monitoring of the impact of these protection methods will be primarily followed through the total number of nests that will be predated as compared to clutches that will remain undisturbed or undergo failed predation attempts. Nest predations will be classified as total (i.e., all eggs have been consumed by the predator and the clutch is destroyed) or partial (i.e., only some eggs have been consumed, nest could be salvaged, and incubation of remaining eggs can continue).

The aim is to ensure the maximum number of clutches that will be able to incubate safely and hatchlings that will be able to exit the nests and be recruited to the population. This will be monitored through post-hatch excavations, conducted within 7-10 days following the first hatching event. During these excavations, the nest is opened, the contents removed, and classified into hatched and unhatched eggs, thus estimating the success of the nest and the total number of hatchlings that have emerged.

Post-hatching monitoring will take place for 5 consecutive years after the completion of the nest protection activities and the final evaluation of the monitoring of the impact will be performed.

However, the true success of the action will not be revealed until more than 15 years after its completion, when some of the saved hatchlings will reach reproductive maturity and return to the site to reproduce. It is highly likely that this is already the case for the site of Kyparissia Bay, where the management techniques applied during the implementation of the LIFE project (LIFE98NAT/GR/005262) did not show any indication of significant recovery of the population, however they are thought to be directly responsible for the steady increase in the number of clutches deposited during the last 15 years.

2.2.8 References

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2.3 Rat Eradication on Strofades Islets

2.3.1. Objectives of the action

- Direct objectives: Eradicate the entire rat's population in the two islands (Arpia and Stamfani islands)
- Indirect objectives: (a) Improve the quality of the Scopoli's shearwater breeding habitat and breeding performance, (b) Improve the breeding/ foraging habitat of other local bird species of the island, (c) Improve the fitness of the migratory species which use the island as a stopover site during the spring/autumn migration.

2.3.2. Target species

- *Calonectris diomedea* is the species that will benefit from this action.
- *Rattus spp.* (main species responsible for predated nests)

2.3.3. Areas of implementation

The study area is the Strofades complex, which includes two islands, Arpia and Stamfani islands (Figure 6). The central coordinate of the complex is 37° 15' 0" North (37.25°), 21° 0' 0" East (21.00°). This 220-ha site is demarcated by the isobath of 50 m and is located south of the southern coast of Zakynthos Island and 28 miles western of the Peloponnesus coast (Katakolo region). The altitude can reach up to 22m above sea level and the total area is 220 ha.

Figure 6. The Strofades complex (Stamfani and Arpia island)

2.3.4. Time period of implementation

The period of implementation needs to be synchronized with the pre-breeding period of the rat species. The reproductive period of the species usually starts in April, therefore the core actions for rat eradication have to be completed between September - March.

2.3.5 Methods and protocols

The methods below follow the methodology used in Guidelines for the eradication of rats from islands within the Falkland group (2003), in Ramsey Island in Wales (2000) and in Puffin Island Anglesey (1998) (Bell, 2019). The same methodology is followed by the most recent rat eradication projects on small islands worldwide. In Greece, this methodology was used during the LIFE project “PanPuffinus” (LIFE19 NAT/MT/000982) in 2022-2025. The methodology applied in this project follows a combined monitoring and control strategy designed to detect, assess, and reduce invasive rodent populations in the study area. Rather than relying on a single technique, a range of complementary tools was used to increase detection probability and improve the reliability of the results. Presented below is an overview of the methods and protocols employed in ‘PanPuffinus’, which will also be implemented in the present project.

1st task (Month 1): Before fieldwork, an initial **assessment of the site** needs to be carried out to identify key habitat features, potential food sources, and areas likely to support rodent activity. Particular attention is given to structural elements such as rock formations, vegetation edges, and human-related features, which often provide shelter or movement corridors for rat species. Monitoring grids are defined in advance and later adjusted in the field where necessary. The spacing of monitoring devices is adapted to the target species and environmental conditions, recognising that smaller species require denser coverage than larger ones.

Fieldwork: Prior to the description of fieldwork tasks, it is important to note that fieldwork is conducted in accordance with basic health and safety procedures. Gloves are used when handling equipment or biological material, both for hygiene reasons and to reduce human scent contamination, which can influence rodent behaviour. All devices are secured in place and, where appropriate, discreetly positioned to minimise disturbance or interference.

2nd task (Month 1): Detection methods: A pre-action task is required in order to estimate at an approximate level the rat species’ population in the islet. To ensure robust detection of rat species presence, several methods are applied simultaneously, each contributing different types of information on rodent presence and activity.

- a) Visual surveys: Visual surveys are carried out during all site visits. Signs such as droppings, footprints, burrows, gnaw marks, and food remains are recorded whenever encountered. Where possible, observations are georeferenced and photographed to support later

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verification.

- b) Camera traps: Camera traps are deployed to confirm rodent presence and provide additional information on activity patterns. These are installed along likely movement routes, including the edges of vegetation, near nesting areas, and close to potential food sources. To maximise effectiveness, cameras are positioned facing along paths rather than across them, and are set to operate primarily during night-time hours. Regular checks need to be carried out to replace batteries, retrieve data, and change the memory cards.
- c) Wax Blocks and Chew Cards: Non-toxic bait-based devices are used extensively due to their practicality and low cost. Flavoured wax blocks and chew cards are placed in sheltered locations and secured to prevent loss. These devices provide indirect evidence of rodent presence through characteristic bite marks.
- d) Tracking Tunnels: Tracking tunnels are used to obtain footprint records, allowing for more reliable identification of species. Each tunnel contains a central lure and an inked surface on which animals leave tracks when passing through. Due to the risk of overlapping prints, tunnels are typically deployed for short periods.
- e) Trapping: Trapping is used selectively to confirm species identification and, where necessary, contribute to population control. Both live traps and kill traps are employed, depending on the context and project objectives. All traps are placed in locations with clear signs of activity and are checked regularly to ensure animal welfare and proper functioning. Protective covers are used to reduce the risk to non-target species.

3rd task (Month 1): First monitoring check, data collection and data analysis: This phase is essential to provide a reference point for later comparison. It also helps optimize the placement of devices. Regular visits are also needed for the maintenance of the equipment and timely identification of any new signs of activity. Data collection follows a consistent format to ensure comparability over time. For each monitoring device, the following information is recorded: a) location (GPS coordinates), b) type of device and bait used, c) presence or absence of activity, d) type of evidence observed (e.g. bite marks, footprints, captures), e) notes on environmental conditions or disturbances. The effectiveness of the action is evaluated by examining changes in detection rates over time. A decrease in signs such as bite marks, footprints, or captures is interpreted as a reduction in rodent activity. Particular attention is given to areas that initially show high levels of activity. These areas are confirmed after the data analysis. Following, these locations are monitored closely to confirm whether reductions are consistent or if further intervention is required. Also, photographic records are taken to support field observations. When this task finishes, the monitoring of the impact of the action begins (2.3.7)

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2.3.6. Expected results

A study was conducted on the Strofades Islands, where rat eradication was carried out in June 2011 (Petrella & Karris, 2012). Following the eradication on Stamfani Island, notable changes were observed in Scopoli's shearwater population. Initially, the population on Stamfani Island, part of the Strofades island complex, consisted of approximately 3,500 pairs, distributed across three sub-colonies (western, southern, and eastern). Rat predation had been a significant factor impacting breeding success, particularly in the western sub-colony, where breeding failures were most pronounced due to the presence of rats. The study indicated that rat eradication was expected to improve the breeding success of Scopoli's shearwater by reducing predation on eggs and chicks, though no precise quantitative increase in population was provided. The study suggests that the removal of rats would likely restore Scopoli's shearwater breeding success to improved levels, since no monitoring was conducted after two summers.

2.3.7. Monitoring of the impact of the action

Monitoring is carried out throughout the duration of the project to track changes in rodent activity and evaluate the effectiveness of the implemented measures. The approach combines different detection methods, allowing for cross-verification of results. Survey frequency is adapted to the phase of the project, with more intensive monitoring during **initial assessment** (2.3.5) and active control periods. Even after a reduction in activity is observed, **long-term monitoring** continues to ensure that no reinvasion occurs. Maintaining a level of surveillance is particularly important in areas with ongoing human access, like the Strofades complex. Therefore, the monitoring and impact assessment plan is structured in phases to ensure the long-term verification of results. The timetable below outlines the sequence, frequency, and objectives of each activity (figure 7).

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Figure 7. The Monitoring and Impact Assessment timeline for rat eradication in Strofades complex

4th task (Month 2-4): Active Monitoring

During this phase, the rat activity is monitored and adaptive changes and maintenance of the monitoring devices are conducted. Moreover, baited devices are replaced and new data are collected. At the end of the 4th month and interim evaluation of the progress is required in order to guide adaptive management of the process. Moreover, monitoring during this phase allows for a rapid response to persistent activity. If rodents are still detected in specific areas, additional devices or control measures can be deployed.

5th task (Month 5-6): Post- action Monitoring

This step is essential for confirming the reduction or absence of rodent activity following implementation. This is a critical phase to confirm whether the action has achieved its immediate objectives. Therefore, intensive monitoring is conducted, whereas bi-weekly devices are being checked and maintained. At the end of Month 6 period, data analysis and preliminary evaluation of the success of the action are done.

6th task (Month 7-12+): Long-term monitoring and Impact assessment

During this phase, monitoring intensity is reduced but remains targeted. Priority is given to high-risk areas such as landing points or human activity zones. Every month, the devices are checked while full-site visual surveys are conducted. Meanwhile, every 6 months, an evaluation of ecological indicators (e.g. nesting success of the Scopoli's shearwater, habitat condition) is conducted. In case of new signs of rodent activity, data should be collected and

immediate actions should be taken following again the same protocol.

2.3.8 References

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Event Codes:

Event	Code	Additional notes
Adult Emergence	1, 2...	Number adult emergences in the order they were encountered
Inundation	I	Comments: metres past nest and cm of sand on top (negative if eroded)
Wash	W	Comments: No additional comments required
Predation	P	Comments: Predator, direction of predation, number eggs/shells found
Attempted Predation	A	Comments: Predator, direction of predation
Vandalism	V	Comments: Any details recorded (especially impact on nest)
Hatch	H	Comments: Number, destination (sea, BoB, animal), disorientation
Found by Hatching	FBH	Comments: As for Hatch
Found by Predation	FBP	Comments: As for Predation
Other	O	Comments: Any details recorded

Track types: (if other types are observed then indicate them by drawing. X = nest location)

Main weather conditions from the previous night: (underline the most appropriate)

- Skies:** clear, light overcast, heavy overcast, completely overcast
Precipitation: none, drizzle, rain, heavy rain, storm
Wind intensity: no wind, weak (breeze), medium, strong, gale
Wind direction: N, NE, E, SE, S, SW, W, NW
Surf on beach: calm, light, moderate, rough, swell

Remarks: (on the environmental conditions, natural and anthropogenic, of the area during the previous 24 hours, e.g. extreme weather conditions, fires/parties on the beach).

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MONITORED NEST SHEET - In situ / Relocated (circle one)

Nest Code

Area		Beach		Sector	
Lay Date		Tag Codes			
Observers					

Protection Method (circle all used)	Date Applied	Additional Notes (Temperature loggers, nest destroyed/lost etc)
Cage		
Screen		
Alleyway/Shading		
Box		
Other:		
Other:		

Nest Location: (circle one) Beach / Hatchery (hatchery position code _____)

Nest Details: (physical data relating to the nest)

Data source	Depths (cm)		Distance to sea (m)	Number of eggs	Notes
	h	H			
Original nest					
Relocated site					

Date relocated: _____ Start Time: _____ End Time: _____

Who did the relocation (names)? _____

Reason for relocation: _____

Nest Position: (for both in situ and relocated nests, draw and label the location along the beach and distance to reference points, and record GPS coordinates)

	Original	Relocated
GPS		
MAP		

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Events during Incubation and Hatching:

Event	Code	Comments Required
Inundation	I	Comments: metres past nest and cm of sand on top (negative if eroded)
Wash	W	Comments: No additional comments required
Predation	P	Comments: Predator, direction of predation, number eggs/shells found
Attempted Predation	A	Comments: Predator, direction of predation
Vandalism	V	Comments: Any details recorded (especially impact on nest)
Other	O	Comments: Any details recorded

Date	Event type	Comments	Date	Event Type	Comments

Hatchling Tracks: (clearly note any observed disorientation)

Date	Number of tracks	Comments (e.g. 2 to sea, 2d to sea, 2d lost, 2 to dog)

Excavation Details:

Excavation Date		Observers	
Depth of egg chamber (H)			

Nest contents	Number	Remarks
Live hatchlings in top 10cm		
Hatched eggs (empty egg shells)		
Dead pipped-hatchlings and their shells		
Live pipped-hatchlings and their shells		
Unhatched eggs with no visible embryos		
Unhatched eggs with dead embryos	Eyespot:	Early:
	Middle:	Late:
Unhatched eggs with live embryos		
Dead hatchlings		
Live hatchlings (exclude those in top 10cm of sand)		

Excavation Remarks: (including nest conditions during excavation: sand, roots, rubbish, maggots etc.)

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